

Self-Reports of Adolescents with Intellectual Disabilities Regarding Their Privacy Awareness

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Abstract

Privacy education equips individuals with intellectual disabilities with essential skills to safeguard their rights and respect others. This study investigates their perceptions of privacy education using a descriptive survey design. The sample consisted of 30 individuals (15 female, 15 male), aged 12–20, enrolled in a Special Education and Rehabilitation Center in Arnavutköy, Istanbul. Data were collected through a 5-item Personal Information Form and two 10-item drawing tests (Draw a Girl and Draw a Boy). Findings showed that most participants were 16–20 years old, single, lived with their families, and had two siblings. Participants reported interest in the opposite sex; male participants noted a desire to be near the opposite sex they preferred and to resemble the figures they drew. All participants indicated that the traits they valued most were wealth and beauty. Overall, understanding the perceptions of individuals with intellectual disabilities toward the opposite sex within the scope of privacy education is critical for supporting their social development and identity formation. The findings suggest that future studies should incorporate expert evaluations in addition to test-based assessments. Moreover, restructuring the content of privacy education in special education to ethically address students' expectations toward the opposite sex and raising awareness in this area are considered important. Additionally, it is suggested that sexual education and privacy topics be included in individualized education programs for individuals with intellectual disabilities, that families and teachers be involved in the program process, and that family training be supported by specialists.

Keywords:

Values,
Ethics,
Morality,
Intellectual Disability,
Drawing Analysis

Özet

Anahtar

Kelimeler:

Değerler,

Etik,

Ahlak,

Zihin Yetersizliği

Resim Analizi

Mahremiyet eğitimi, zihin yetersizliği bireylerin haklarını korumasını ve başkalarına saygı göstermesini sağlayan önemli kazanımları içerir. Bu araştırma, zihin yetersizliği bireylerin mahremiyet eğitimi konusundaki duygu ve düşüncelerini incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Çalışma, betimsel tarama modeli ile yürütülmüş olup, İstanbul Arnavutköy'deki bir Özel Eğitim ve Rehabilitasyon Merkezine devam eden 12–20 yaş arası 30 bireyi (15 kız, 15 erkek) kapsamaktadır. Veri toplama araçları 5 soruluk Kişisel Bilgi Formu ile 10'ar soruluk Bir Kız Çiz Testi ve Bir Erkek Çiz Testidir. Bulgular, katılımcıların çoğunlukla 16–20 yaş, bekar, aileleriyle yaşayan ve 2 kardeşe sahip olduğunu göstermektedir. Katılımcılar karşı cinse ilgi duyduklarını; erkekler beğendikleri karşı cinsle aynı ortamda bulunmayı ve çizim karakterlerine benzemeyi istediklerini belirtmiş, tüm katılımcılar ise en beğendikleri özelliklerin zenginlik ve güzellik olduğunu ifade etmiştir. Sonuç olarak zihin yetersizliği bulunan bireylerin mahremiyet eğitimi bağlamında, karşı cinse yönelik duygu ve düşüncelerinin anlaşılması; bu bireylerin sosyal gelişimlerini desteklemek ve kimlik oluşum süreçlerini güçlendirmek açısından önem taşımaktadır. Bulgular doğrultusunda, gelecekteki araştırmalarda yalnızca testlere değil, uzman görüşleriyle desteklenen değerlendirmelere de yer verilmesi önerilmektedir. Özel eğitimde mahremiyet eğitimi içeriklerinin, öğrencilerin karşı cinse yönelik beklentilerini etik ilkeler çerçevesinde ele alacak biçimde yeniden yapılandırılması ve bu konuda farkındalık kazandırılması önem taşımaktadır. Ayrıca, zihinsel yetersizliği olan bireylere yönelik bireyselleştirilmiş eğitim programlarına cinsel eğitim ve mahremiyet konularının dâhil edilmesi; aile ve öğretmenlerin program sürecine katılması ve uzmanlar tarafından aile eğitimlerinin desteklenmesi önerilmektedir.

1. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a developmental period that presents unique challenges for individuals with intellectual disabilities. During this stage, concepts such as gender identity, bodily changes, and privacy may be understood and expressed with more limited skills compared to typically developing peers. For instance, a study by Çelik and Yücel (2023) reported significant differences in the physical, social, and emotional aspects of sexual development among adolescents with intellectual disabilities, based on parental reports (Çelik & Yücel, 2023, p. 801). In this context, a study by Yalçın, Erkoç, and Şişman (2023) addressed whether privacy education is equivalent to sexual education. The researchers emphasized that, according to parents, sexual education and privacy education are not the same. Privacy education goes beyond sexual knowledge, aiming to raise awareness in children about personal space and boundaries (Yalçın, Erkoç, & Şişman, 2023, p. 41).

Privacy education, which also encompasses sexual education, particularly aims to help children recognize both their own personal space and that of others, learn to respect these boundaries, and maintain them within social life (Akcan, 2016, p. 77). In other words, individuals may exhibit behaviors inconsistent with protecting their personal privacy, such as engaging in sexualized behaviors in inappropriate settings, showing interest in their own sex, or forming relationships with members of the opposite sex. Ultimately, the misuse of sexuality by individuals with intellectual disabilities is associated with weak social skills, impaired reasoning abilities, and insufficient privacy education (Çakmak & Çakmak, 2018, p. 49).

This limited understanding and difficulty in self-expression create risks regarding the nature of privacy and its boundaries. In their study, Karaca and Çiçek (2024) emphasized that adolescents with intellectual disabilities who lack an appropriate sense of privacy are more likely to engage in risky sexual behaviors and be vulnerable to abuse (Karaca & Çiçek, 2022, p. 83).

As can be inferred, privacy education can be considered a competence that enables individuals with special needs to protect their own rights while showing respect for others. Young individuals with disabilities who have not received privacy education may express their thoughts and feelings more comfortably through drawing. Indeed, Kaytez (2018) highlights that, during interviews, conditions such as a safe environment, genuine interest, avoidance of pressure, casual conversation, use of the child's language, visual representation, and play-based concretization are essential to allow children to discuss past experiences of abuse more freely (Kaytez, Yücesoy & Kadan, 2028, p. 19).

Sex education, a crucial component of privacy education for individuals with intellectual disabilities, is addressed in the study by Hartini, Chamidah, and Siti Herini (2021). According to their research, adolescents with intellectual disabilities (ID) have sexual needs and may experience sexual behavior issues similar to their typically developing peers. In fact, due to their limited understanding of sexuality, they are at a higher risk of engaging in unsafe sexual behaviors (Hartini, Chamidah, & Siti Herini, 2021, p. 104). These findings underscore the importance of sexual education to enable adolescents with intellectual disabilities to develop healthy sexual behaviors and lead safe lives.

Given the significance of this education, it is essential to analyze the privacy awareness of adolescents with intellectual disabilities. For this purpose, participants were asked to draw pictures, and subsequent discussions based on these drawings were used to examine their awareness of privacy. Moreover, as individuals with intellectual disabilities may have difficulty expressing such important issues verbally, drawing provides a means for them to communicate more comfortably.

2. METHOD

This study aims to determine the feelings and thoughts of adolescents with intellectual disabilities (ID) regarding privacy education. The research was designed using the descriptive survey model, a qualitative research method. Participants with intellectual disabilities were instructed to draw one girl and one boy, allowing them to express themselves more comfortably both verbally and in writing through their drawings. In this context, the descriptive survey model of qualitative research was chosen as an approach that seeks to gain an in-depth understanding of individuals' experiences, perceptions, feelings, and thoughts (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018, p. 41).

Unlike quantitative research, the qualitative approach focuses on verbal and visual data rather than numerical data and seeks to uncover the meanings underlying events. The descriptive survey model, in particular, aims to depict a situation as it exists, whether in the past or present (Karasar, 2006, p. 14).

The study participants consisted of 30 individuals with intellectual disabilities, aged 12–18, attending a Special Education and Rehabilitation Center in the Arnavutköy district of Istanbul, including 15 females and 15 males. Participants were selected using purposive sampling in line with the research objectives. This method was preferred because it allows for the selection of individuals who are most knowledgeable and appropriate for the study's purpose. Indeed, according to Yıldırım and Şimşek (2018), purposive sampling is a qualitative research method that enables the selection of individuals or cases with the most relevant information for the research aim. In this approach, the goal is not to create a representative sample but to obtain in-depth information about the research topic (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018, p. 21). In this study, participants were selected with the aim of reflecting the feelings and thoughts of individuals with intellectual disabilities regarding privacy education.

Two data collection instruments were used in this study: (1) a Personal Information Form (PIF) consisting of five questions, and (2) the Draw a Girl Test (DGT) and Draw a Boy Test (DBT), each consisting of ten questions. Prior to the study, all necessary ethical approvals were obtained. Voluntary participation consent was secured from the school administration and teachers. Once all permissions were granted, the data collection process commenced. The drawings obtained from participants were analyzed using qualitative methods to reflect the individuals' thoughts and perceptions regarding privacy.

3. Findings

The findings obtained from the Personal Information Form (PIF), the Draw a Girl Test (DGT), and the Draw a Boy Test (DBT) for adolescents with intellectual disabilities are presented in the tables below.

3.1. Demographic Characteristics of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities

The demographic characteristics of the adolescents with intellectual disabilities (ID) who participated in the study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Analysis of the Demographic Distribution of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (ID)

Variable	Groups	Number of Participants
Gender	Kız	15
	Erkek	15
Age	12-14	8
	15-18	18
	19 and above	4
Drawing Ability	Low	8
	Moderate	19
	High	3
Sexual Development	Present	30
	Absent	0
Additional Disability Type	Intellectual Disability	22
	Down Syndrome	8
Total		30

According to the demographic analysis presented in Table 1, the study included a total of 30 adolescents with intellectual disabilities, comprising 15 females (50%) and 15 males (50%). Among the participants, 8 were aged 12–14 years (early adolescence), 18 were 15–18 years old (middle adolescence), and 4 were 19 years and older (late adolescence). The fewest participants were in the early adolescence group (12–14 years), while the majority were in the middle adolescence group (15–18 years). Regarding drawing ability, 8 participants were assessed as having low drawing skills, 19 as moderate, and 3 as high. Based on teacher reports, all 30 participants, selected through purposive sampling, had reached sexual development. In terms of additional diagnoses, 22 participants were identified with intellectual disability (ID) and 8 with Down syndrome (DS).

3.2. Analysis Findings of the Draw a Girl Test (DGT) for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities

The findings of the Draw a Girl Test (DGT) for adolescents with intellectual disabilities (ID) regarding privacy education are presented in the tables below.

Table 2: Analysis Findings on Behavioral Patterns in Drawings from the DGT for Adolescents with Intellectual Disabilities (ID)

Variable	Groups – Participant Responses	N
Behavior Depicted in the Drawing (What is she doing?)	Sitting with a male	16
	Experiencing a happy moment	2
	Working	2
	Going to school	2
	Doing house cleaning	1
	Crying	1
	Sitting with friends	1
	Giving flowers to her boyfriend	1
	Playing a game	1

	Picking flowers	1
	A mermaid sitting in the park holding a coffee	1
	Going home	1
Total		30

In Table 2, among the participants with intellectual disabilities completing the *Draw-a-Girl Test* (DGT), 1 participant drew a girl crying, 1 doing house cleaning, 1 sitting with a friend, 1 playing with a friend, 1 picking flowers for her boyfriend, 1 drinking coffee, and 1 going home. Additionally, 2 participants depicted her going to school, 2 showed her working, and 2 illustrated her experiencing a happy moment. The drawings of 16 participants indicated that the girl was sitting and spending time with boys.

The findings of the *Draw-a-Girl Test for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities* (DGTIID) are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Analysis Findings Regarding the Age of the Character Depicted in DGTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Category	N
Age Depicted in the Drawing	5-9 years	2
	10-15 years	8
	16-20 years	16
	21-30 years	3
	30-40 years	1
Total		30

In Table 3, the ages of the characters depicted by the participants with intellectual disabilities (ID) are presented as follows: 2 participants illustrated characters aged 5–9, 8 participants depicted characters aged 10–15, 16 participants drew characters aged 16–20, 3 participants illustrated characters aged 21–30, and 1 participant depicted a character aged 30–40. The smallest group consisted of two participants who drew characters aged 5–9, while the largest group consisted of sixteen participants who drew characters aged 16–20.

The findings of the “Draw a Girl Test” administered to individuals with intellectual disabilities (DGTIID) are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Analysis Findings Regarding the Marital Status of the Character in DGTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Marital Status of the Character	Married	5
	Single	25
Total		30

In Table 4, it was determined that 5 participants perceived the character as married, while 25 participants perceived the character as single.

The findings of the Draw a Girl Test for an Individual with Intellectual Disabilities (DGTIID) are presented in the tables below.

Table 5: Analysis Findings Regarding With Whom the Character Lives in DGTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
With Whom the Character Lives	With family	21
	Alone	9
Total		30

In Table 5, it was found that 21 participants stated that the character lives with their family, whereas 9 participants stated that the character lives alone.

The findings of the Draw a Girl Test for an Individual with Intellectual Disabilities (DGTIID) are presented in **Table 6**.

Table 6: Analysis Findings Regarding the Number of Siblings of the Character in DGTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Number of Siblings	0	5
	1	9
	2	12
	3	3
	4	1
Total		30

In Table 6, 5 participants stated that the character has no siblings. Nine participants reported that the character has one sibling, 12 reported two siblings, 3 reported three siblings, and 1 participant stated that the character has four siblings.

The findings of the Draw a Girl Test for Adolescents with Intellectual Disabilities (DGTIID) regarding privacy education are presented in the tables below

Table 7: Analysis Findings Regarding the Character's Willingness to Be in the Character's Place in DGTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Willingness to be in the Character's Place	Yes: Because they look like me	26
	No: Because they are weak and committed suicide	1
	No: Because they are the opposite sex	3
Total		30

In Table 7, the analysis revealed that 26 participants wished to be in the place of the character in the drawing, while 4 participants did not. The primary reason for wanting to be in the character's place was that they identified with or saw themselves in the character. Conversely, the main reason for not wanting to be in the character's place was that the character was of the opposite sex, leading to reluctance, disagreement, or discomfort with the opposite-sex behaviors depicted in the drawing.

In Table 7, 26 participants stated that they would like to be in the character's place, whereas 4 participants stated that they would not.

The findings of the Draw a Girl Test for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (DGTIID) are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Analysis Findings Regarding the Character’s Employment Status in DGTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Employment Status	Yes	7
	No	23
Total		30

In Table 8, it was determined that 7 participants depicted the character as employed, whereas 23 participants stated that the character was not employed.

The findings of the Draw a Girl Test for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (DGTIID) are presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Analysis Findings Regarding the Desires of the Character in DGTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Desires	To get married (with their partner)	18
	To be rich	10
	To have a friend	1
	To be beautiful	1
Total		30

In Table 9, 18 participants stated that the character desires to marry their partner, 10 participants stated that the character wants to be rich, 1 participant stated that the character wants to have a friend, and 1 participant stated that the character wants to be beautiful.

The findings of the Draw a Girl Test (DGTIID) administered to individuals with intellectual disabilities are presented in the following tables.

Table 10: Analysis Findings Regarding the Most Liked Traits of the Character in DGTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Most Liked Trait	Being helpful	7
	Being rich / generous	8
	Being beautiful	8
	Having no bad habits	2
	Helping her mother	1
	Not overthinking	1
	Being smart and beautiful	1
	Drawing pictures	1
	Knowing what she wants	1
	Total	

In Table 10, participants’ most liked traits were as follows: 2 participants stated “having no bad habits,” 1 stated “helping her mother,” 1 “not overthinking,” 1 “being smart and beautiful,” 1 “drawing pictures,” and 1 “knowing what she wants.” The most frequently mentioned traits were being helpful (7 participants), being rich/generous (8 participants), and being beautiful (8 participants).

The findings of the Draw a Girl Test (DGTIID) for individuals with intellectual disabilities are presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Analysis Findings Regarding the Least Liked Traits of the Character in DGTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Least Liked Trait	Being naughty / bad	6
	Getting angry easily	9
	Being ugly	5
	Being introverted	2
	Constantly buying gifts for friends	2
	Veing very quarrelsome	1
	‘Bad because she is a girl’ (male participant)	1
	‘What will people say?’ concern	1
	Wanting something all the time	1
	Not reading books	1
	‘No good traits because she is a girl’ (male participant)	1
Total		30

In Table 11, the least liked traits identified by participants included: 1 participant stating “very quarrelsome,” 1 “concern for what people will say,” 1 “wanting things constantly,” 1 “not reading books,” 1 stating the character is bad solely because she is a girl, 2 stating the character is introverted, and 2 stating the character constantly buys gifts for friends. Additionally, 5 participants disliked the character for being ugly, 6 for being naughty or bad, and 9 for getting angry easily.

3.3. Analysis Findings of the Draw-a-Boy Test (DBTIID) for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities

The findings of the Draw-a-Boy Test (DBTIID), conducted with adolescents with Intellectual Disabilities (ID) regarding privacy education, are presented below.

Table 12: Analysis Findings Related to the Depicted Behavior in DBTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N	
Depicted Behavior (What is he doing?)	Sitting with a girl	15	
	Working	3	
	Doing house cleaning	2	
	Going home	2	
	Going to school	2	
	Experiencing a happy moment	2	
	Waiting for a friend for a match	1	
	Giving flowers to a girl	1	
	Playing a game	1	
	Picking flowers	1	
	Total		30

The findings from Table 12 indicate that among the DBTIID participants, 1 participant was depicted waiting for a friend for a match, 1 was giving a flower to a girl, 1 was playing a game, 1 was picking flowers, 2 were experiencing a happy moment, 2 were going to school, 2 were going home, 2 were doing house cleaning, 3 were working, and 15 were depicted sitting with a girl.

The findings of the Draw a Boy Test for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (DBTIID) are presented in Table 13

Table 13. Analysis Findings of the Depicted Character's Age in DBTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Age	5-10 years	4
	10-15 years	9
	16-20 years	11
	21-30 years	3
	30-35 years	2
	36-40 years	1
Total		30

In Table 13, the age of the characters depicted by DBTIID participants was found as follows: 1 character aged 36–40 years, 2 characters aged 30–35 years, 3 characters aged 21–30 years, 4 characters aged 5–10 years, 9 characters aged 10–15 years, and 11 characters aged 16–20 years.

The findings regarding the marital status of the characters in the Draw a Boy Test for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (DBTIID) are presented in Table 14.

Table 14: Analysis Findings of the Character's Marital Status in DBTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Marital Status	Married	5
	Single	25
Total		30

According to Table 14, among the characters depicted by DBTIID participants, 5 were married, while 25 were single.

The findings of the Draw a Boy Test for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (DBTIID) are presented in Table 15 below.

Table 15: Analysis Findings of With Whom the Character Lives in DBTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
With Whom the Character Lives	With family	27
	Alone	3
Total		30

According to Table 15, among the characters depicted by DBTIID participants, 27 live with their family, while 3 live alone.

The findings of the Draw a Boy Test for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (DBTIID) regarding the number of siblings of the depicted characters are presented in Table 16.

Table 16: Analysis Findings of the Character's Number of Siblings in DBTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Number of Siblings	0	6
	1	9
	2	11
	3	4
Total		30

According to Table 16, among the characters depicted by the participants, 6 had no siblings, 9 had one sibling, 11 had two siblings, and 4 had three siblings.

The findings of the Draw a Boy Test for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (DBTIID) are presented below.

Table 17: Analysis Findings of the Character's Employment Status in DBTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Employment Status	Yes	5
	No	23
Total		30

According to Table 17, among the characters depicted by the DBTIID participants, 5 are employed, whereas 23 are not employed.

The findings of the Draw a Boy Test for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (DBTIID) regarding desires are presented in Table 18.

Table 18: Analysis Findings of the Character's Wishes in DBTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Character's Wishes	To get married	12
	"To be rich"	6
	To spend time with beautiful girls	9
	To become a teacher	1
Total	To have a better job	2
		30

According to Table 18, among the characters depicted by the participants, 12 desire to get married, 6 wish to be rich, 9 want to spend time with beautiful girls, 1 wants to become a teacher, and 2 aspire to have a better job.

The findings of the Draw a Boy Test for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (DBTIID) regarding the characters' desire to be in the depicted position are presented in Table 19.

Table 19: Participants' Desire to Be in the Character's Place in DBTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Desire to Be in the Character's Place	Yes: Because he resembles me	29
	No: Because he was weak and committed suicide	1
Total		30

According to Table 19, 29 participants indicated that they would like to be in the position of the character they depicted, while 1 participant indicated that they would not.

The findings of the Draw a Boy Test for Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (DBTIID), related to the privacy education of adolescents with intellectual disabilities (ID), are presented in Table 20.

Table 20: Most Liked Traits of the Depicted Character in DBTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Most Liked Trait	Being helpful	5
	Being wealthy	9
	Being good-looking	8
	Being respectful to family	2
	Being respectful	1
	Playing scary games	1
	Being intelligent	1
	Giving gifts	1
	Being a gambler	1
	Being tolerant	1
	Total	

According to Table 20, the findings indicate that the aspects of the characters depicted by the participants that were most admired include: 1 character playing frightening games, 1 being intelligent, 1 receiving gifts, 1 being a gambler, 1 being tolerant, 1 being respectful, 2 showing respect to their family, 5 being helpful, 8 being beautiful, and 9 being wealthy. These features represent the qualities that participants most appreciated in the characters they drew.

The findings related to the Draw-a-Boy Test (DBTIID) for adolescents with intellectual disabilities regarding privacy education are presented in Table 21.

Table 21: Least Liked Traits of the Depicted Character in DBTIID

Variable	Participant Response / Group	N
Least Liked Trait	Being naughty / bad	5
	Getting angry easily	7
	Being unattractive	8
	Being shy	2
	Having no bad traits	2
	Being very aggressive	1
	Being perfectionist	1
	Being stingy	1
	Yelling at his mother	1
	Making fun of others	1
	Making bad friends	1
Total		30

According to Table 21, the findings indicate that the least liked traits of the characters depicted in the Draw-a-Boy Test (ZYBBBEÇT) by the participants were as follows: 1 character being very quarrelsome, 1 being perfectionist, 1 being stingy, 1 yelling at their mother, 1 mocking others, 1 having bad friends, 2 having no bad habits, 2 being shy, 5 being naughty, 7 being quick-tempered, and 8 being unattractive. These traits were identified as the least favored aspects of the characters drawn by the participants.

3. DISCUSSION

The research findings indicate that individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (ID) exhibit interest in the opposite sex. Similar results were reported in the study conducted by Sezik, Alp, and Aksoy (2024). In this systematic review, the tendencies of individuals with special needs to show interest in the opposite sex were observed (Sezik, Alp, & Aksoy, 2024, p. 47).

In the study, most participants expressing interest in the opposite sex were within the 16–20 age range. This finding aligns with Derman's (2008) delineation of middle adolescence, which corresponds to the 15–18 age range. During middle adolescence, young people tend to distance themselves from their parents and increasingly turn to peer groups; within this context, behaviors of closeness, particularly with the opposite sex, are commonly observed (Derman, 2008, p. 62).

The research findings also indicate that the majority of participants live with their families. Families play a critical role in providing privacy education. Martı (2020) emphasizes that parents should adopt a relaxed and natural communication style when discussing such topics with their children. Attempting to instill awareness of privacy through fear or anxiety may lead to vulnerability and trust issues in social life. Therefore, it is essential to address the topic gently and openly, prioritizing explanations over prohibitions (Martı, 2020, p. 82).

Furthermore, the study revealed that individuals with Intellectual Disabilities (ID) expressed a desire to marry. According to Berger and Luckmann (2008), the marital aspirations of individuals with special needs are often related to fear of loneliness and social connections. Marriage, as a symbolic universe representing institutional order, addresses the social needs of individuals. Additionally, pre-marital experiences may lead to perceiving marriage as a form of "escape" or "rescue." Due to societal barriers, individuals with disabilities may perceive themselves as a burden, making concepts such as sharing and compatibility salient in partner selection. Expanding social networks and strengthening relationships with family and work circles are also among the motivating factors for marriage (Demir, 2018, p. 111).

The findings also show that participants tend to desire resemblance to the characters depicted in their drawings. This may reflect participants' expressions of themselves, their parents, or relatives. Self-expression through drawing is an effective technique, particularly for children and individuals with special needs, for assessing self-awareness, self-concept, emotions, and social skills. Through their drawings, individuals can convey their inner world and emotional states, supporting psychological assessment and therapeutic processes (Yavuzer, 1994; Capacchione, 2012, p. 47).

Finally, the study indicates that both girls and boys with special needs show interest in the physical attractiveness of the opposite sex. In a study by Donnachie, Jones, and Jahoda (2021), individuals with intellectual disabilities evaluated physical attractiveness, such as facial beauty, in a manner similar to individuals without intellectual disabilities. This finding suggests that the social and emotional perceptions of individuals with special needs are largely comparable to those of the general population (Donnachie, Jones, & Jahoda, 2021, p. 101).

4. CONCLUSION

This study examined the thoughts and feelings of adolescents with special needs (intellectual disabilities, ID) regarding privacy education through drawing tests and personal information forms. According to the research findings:

- The majority of ID participants tended to sit with members of the opposite sex.
- The participants were primarily aged 16–20, corresponding to the middle and late stages of adolescence.
- Most participants were single and lived with their families.
- The majority of participants had two siblings, and most were not employed.
- ID male participants expressed a desire to spend time with attractive girls in their drawings.
- Participants tended to identify with the characters they drew and most admired the wealth and beauty attributes of these characters.

These results indicate that adolescents with ID show interest in the opposite sex during their social and emotional development, maintain social relationships within the family environment, and express themselves through idealized characters. Furthermore, drawing-based assessments are shown to be an effective tool for understanding the emotions and social perceptions of individuals with special needs.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that the planning of privacy education for individuals with ID take into account their social interests and emotional experiences. Educational programs should be structured considering the participants' age, gender, social environment, and personal perceptions.

4.1. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed for privacy education for individuals with intellectual disabilities:

1. Individualization of Educational Programs: Privacy education should be designed considering the individuals' age, gender, social environment, and personal perceptions.
2. Encouraging Family Participation: Families should discuss privacy-related topics with children in a natural and gentle manner, providing guidance through open communication rather than fear or prohibition.
3. Drawing- and Art-Based Assessments: Art- and drawing-based techniques can serve as effective tools to understand the emotional states and social perceptions of individuals with intellectual disabilities.
4. Supporting Perceptions of the Opposite Sex: The interest of individuals with intellectual disabilities in the opposite sex and their social interactions should be guided safely and appropriately through counseling and support programs.

4.1.1. Recommendations for Future Research

- It is recommended to examine the perceptions of privacy among individuals with intellectual disabilities across different age groups and types of disabilities in a comparative manner.
- In addition to drawing-based methods, incorporating expert evaluations and multidimensional assessment tools may provide more comprehensive and reliable findings.
- Longitudinal studies investigating the relationship between social and emotional development and privacy education in greater depth would be valuable.

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